

Synthesis and biological studies of 16–26 membered tetraazamacrocyclic complexes of tin(II)

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Template condensation reaction of dicarboxylic acids (malonic, succinic, glutaric, adipic or phthalic) with primary diamines 1,2-diaminoethane, 1,3-diaminopropane or diethylenetriamine in 1 : 2 : 2 molar ratio gives a new series of 16 to 26 membered tetraazamacrocyclic complexes of composition $[Sn(MaC_n)Cl_2]$. All the complexes are stable and monomeric in nature. The spectral studies confirm the proposed framework of the new macrocyclic complexes and the coordination of amide nitrogen to the central tin metal. An octahedral geometry for these complexes has been proposed. Their biological activities have also been studied.

The coordination chemistry of macrocycles is an expeditiously expanding domain of research¹. Macrocyclic complexes are very active part of metalloenzymes and industrial catalysis. Synthetic macrocyclic ligands resemble with natural macrocycles such as porphyrins in electronic properties and reactivity. A large number of synthetic macrocyclic complexes have been obtained by the condensation of di- or polyamines with aldehyde or ketons². These display a number of features of chemical interest³ including the formation of both mononuclear and dinuclear metal complexes. Many of such complexes have unusual structures. Small substrate molecules and ions are bound as bridging ligands between the metal centres in the dinuclear complexes⁴. These dinuclear complexes are used as oxidation catalysts for organic substrates⁵. In view of these interesting aspects we have prepared the metal-controlled macrocyclic tetraamides from diacides with di- and triamines. The results of these studies alongwith the biological studies of the resulting macrocyclic complexes of tin(II) are presented here.

Results and Discussion

All the solid complexes are stable at room temperature and non-hygroscopic. The molar conductance values for the complexes show them to be non-electrolytes. All the complexes are slightly soluble in common organic solvents but freely soluble in DMF and DMSO. Molecular weight of these complexes indicate their monomeric nature. The physical and analytical data of the complexes are given in Table 1. The elemental analyses agree with the chemical formulae of the compounds.

Table 1. Analytical and physical data of the complexes*

Compd.	M.p. °C	Metal % :	
		Found (Calcd.)	Mol. wt. : Found (Calcd.)
C ₁₄ H ₂₄ O ₄ N ₄ Cl ₂ Sn	211	37.75 (38.29)	297 (310)
C ₂₀ H ₂₀ O ₄ N ₄ Cl ₂ Sn	119	20.21 (20.82)	538 (570)
C ₁₆ H ₂₈ O ₄ N ₄ Cl ₂ Sn	197	21.80 (22.39)	493 (530)
C ₂₂ H ₂₄ O ₄ N ₄ Cl ₂ Sn	135	19.22 (19.85)	572 (598)
C ₁₄ H ₂₆ O ₄ N ₆ Cl ₂ Sn	186	21.93 (22.31)	503 (532)
C ₁₆ H ₃₀ O ₄ N ₆ Cl ₂ Sn	143	21.77 (22.31)	531 (560)
C ₁₈ H ₃₄ O ₄ N ₆ Cl ₂ Sn	203	19.51 (20.19)	561 (588)
C ₂₀ H ₃₈ O ₄ N ₆ Cl ₂ Sn	177	18.75 (19.27)	605 (616)

*All compounds gave satisfactory N and Cl analyses.

Disappearance of the infrared absorption bands due to hydroxyl and primary amino groups, provides evidence for the cyclization and the proposed macrocyclic framework. The spectra of all the complexes show a single peak in the region 3118–3273 cm⁻¹ due to NH stretching mode of amide group or secondary amino groups of diethylenetriamine. The amide I, II, III and IV groups present in plane deformations are indicated by the bands at 1669–1720, 1460–1533, 1237–1272 and 663–680, respectively^{6,7}. In marked contrast to the complexes characteristic bands due to ν_{Sn-N} vibration exhibit at 441–480 cm⁻¹, unequivocally supports that four nitrogen atoms of the complexes are coordinating to the tin metal⁶.

On comparing the proton-NMR spectra of the starting compounds and their complexes, it was observed that no signal is present for the NH₂ and OH groups in the respective metal complexes. It is an evidence that the proposed

macrocyclic skeleton has been formed through the condensation. In the spectra of all the complexes, a broad signal is observed at δ 8.06–8.41 due to amide CO–NH⁷. In the spectra of the complexes, a multiplet due to the methylene protons⁸ appear at δ 3.28–3.56. The spectra of [Sn(MaC₃)Cl₂] and [Sn(MaC₄)Cl₂] show multiplets at δ 1.93–2.11 assignable to middle methylene protons of propane chain⁹. Furthermore, a multiplet appearing at δ 6.19–6.28 can be assigned to secondary amino C–NH–C of diethylenetriamine moiety¹⁰. A singlet at δ 3.01 and 3.07 may be ascribed to methylene protons of malonic acid and succinic acid, respectively. A multiplet observed at δ 3.21–3.24 and 3.24, are assigned to the methylene portion of glutaric acid and adipic acid, respectively, which are adjacent to the nitrogen atom. In the spectra of [Sn(MaC₂)Cl₂] and [Sn(MaC₄)Cl₂], a multiplet observed at δ 6.98–7.17 corresponds to the phenyl proton¹¹.

The above interpretation of the spectral studies confirms that the ligands act as tetradentate chelating agents having four coordination sites; accordingly a hexacoordinating environment around the tin metal atom can be proposed.

Fungicidal activity of the compounds was evaluated by the radial growth method¹¹ using czapek's agar medium in concentrations, 50, 100 and 200 ppm in methanol against *Fusarium oxysporum* and *Aspergillus niger*. Bactericidal activity of the compounds was evaluated by the inhibition zone technique¹² in concentrations 500 and 1000 ppm in methanol against *Pseudomonas cepacicola* (–) and *Escherichia coli* (–). The results indicate that fungitoxicity and bacteriotoxicity of the present compounds are significantly enhanced on chelation.

Experimental

All the chemicals used including malonic acid, succinic acid, glutaric acid, adipic acid and phthalic acid (Fluka) were used as such. 1,2-Diaminoethane, 1,3-diaminopropane and diethylenetriamine (E. Merck) were used as obtained. SnCl₂·2H₂O (B.D.H.) was used without further purification.

[Sn(MaC₁)Cl₂]; 2,6,11,15-tetraoxo-1,7,10,16-tetraazacyclooctadecanetin(II) chloride : The reaction was carried out in 1 : 2 : 2 molar ratio. SnCl₂·2H₂O (1.04 g) was dissolved in minimum amount of dry methanol (30 ml) and cooled in an ice-bath. To it was added methanolic solution of 1,2-diaminoethane (0.55 g) followed by addition of glutaric acid (1.22 g) solution in MeOH. The resulting mixture was stirred for 24–25 h. The resulting solid was washed with the same solvent and dried under reduced pressure.

[Sn(MaC₂)Cl₂]; 3,4,11,12-dibenzo-2,5,10,13-tetraoxo-1,6,14-tetraazacyclohexadecanetin(II) chloride : To

SnCl₂·2H₂O (1.0 g) dissolved in methanol (30 ml), 1,2-diaminoethane (0.53 g) and phthalic acid (1.47 g) were added and the solution was stirred at room temperature for 24–25 h. The product obtained was washed with MeOH and dried under reduced pressure.

[Sn(MaC₃)Cl₂]; 2,6,12,16, tetraoxo-1,7,11,17-tetraazacyclododecanetin(II) chloride : The procedure was the same as described above. The reagents used were SnCl₂·2H₂O (1.0 g), 1,3-diaminopropane (0.65 g) and glutaric acid (1.17 g).

[Sn(MaC₄)Cl₂]; 3,4,12,13-dibenzo-2,5,11,14-tetraoxo-1,6,10,15-tetraazacyclooctadecanetin(II) chloride : The complex was synthesized by the above method, using SnCl₂·2H₂O (1.0 g), 1,3-diaminopropane (0.66 g) and phthalic acid (1.49 g).

[Sn(MaC₅)Cl₂]; 2,4,12,14-tetraoxo-1,5,11,15-tetraazacyclododecanetin(II) chloride : This compound was isolated by the procedure as detailed for [Sn(MaC₁)Cl₂]. The reagents used were SnCl₂·2H₂O (1.0 g), diethylenetriamine (0.91 g) and malonic acid (0.92 g).

[Sn(MaC₆)Cl₂]; 2,5,13,16-tetraoxo-1,6,12,17-tetraazacyclododecanetin(II) chloride : The preparation was analogous to the above. Succinic acid was used in place of malonic acid.

Fig. 1

[Sn(MaC₇)Cl₂]; 4,6,14,18-tetraoxo-1,7,13,19-tetraazacyclododecanetin(II) chloride and [Sn(MaC₈)Cl₂]; 2,7,15,20-tetraoxo-1,8,14,21-tetraazacyclohexadecanetin(II) chloride : For these complexes, glutaric and adipic acids were used as diacids in corresponding amount of

Note

$\text{SnCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$. Thus, a new series of 16–26 membered tetraazamacrocyclic complexes of tin(II) were derived by the template condensation of dicarboxylic acids with diamines or diethylenetriamine as shown in Fig. 1.

The purity of the compounds was checked by TLC on silica gel-G using anhydrous methanol and tetrahydrofuran as solvent.

Conductivity was measured with a Systronic 305 conductivity bridge in dry dimethylformamide. Molecular weight was determined by Rast camphor method. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Nicolet Magna FT-IR 550 spectrophotometer and ^1H NMR spectra ($\text{DMSO}-d_6$) on a FX 90 Q spectrometer using TMS as the internal standard. Nitrogen and chlorine were estimated by Kjeldahl's and Volhard's method, respectively. Tin was estimated as tin oxide gravimetrically.

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